

GENERAL CLASSIFICATION OF THE FORM OF STATE STRUCTURE

Botirova Gulsanam

2nd year student of the Department of English Philology, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Faculty of Romance-German

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5713558>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th November 2021
Accepted: 10th November 2021
Online: 15th November 2021

KEY WORDS

right, freedom, political right, law, constitution, democracy, freedom of speech, right of residence, freedom of conscience, socio-economic rights.

ABSTRACT

The protection and promotion of human rights and freedoms is a key criterion for building a democratic state governed by the rule of law and a prosperous civil society. Therefore, in any country, first of all, the rights and freedoms of citizens are a priority. The personal rights of citizens are natural, inalienable right. This paper covers this theme.

The state structure is the organization of state power on the territory of the country attitude of state bodies in the regions, central state bodies is a separate form of designation. Such relations (center-region relations) are in small states easy to install, difficult to solve in large, multinational states. State The issues of structural form are deep and comprehensive in the science of the theory of state and law studied. Three views of the state structure according to the theory of state and law. They are the Unitary State, the Federal State and the Confederate State. A federal state is a union of state structures, known as a federation is a union of independent entities. Some of the subjects of the federation countries are independent and some of their powers are voluntary to the federatio and all subjects

have the same legal status. Such In states, the territory of the federation consists of the territory of the subjects, the federation constitutions of subjects, citizenship, separate legislation, executive, judiciary will be a body of power. The United States, India, Brazil, Russia can be mentioned. A unitary state is a simple form of state structure, the structure of which is different there are no state structures, territorial units do not have independence. Single the constitution, unified citizenship, the supreme legislature, the executive and the judiciary is structured and operates in a centralized manner. These are a number of countries France, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan can be added. Uzbekistan is also a unitary state. But in its structure 269 there are also

features specific to some federal states. For example, the structure of the state in Uzbekistan was typical. There is the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Its constitution, laws, territory, citizenship, supreme legislative, executive and judicial authorities. Relations between Karakalpakstan and Uzbekistan are based on federal relations not built. If a federation is a union of several equal subjects, here there are no equal federation subjects. Constitution of Uzbekistan, The laws of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are binding and The laws of Karakalpakstan fully recognize the supremacy of the laws of Uzbekistan. However, in Karakalpakstan, its position, which is typical of the state structure, is different. There are cases that differ from other structures of Uzbekistan. We will discuss this in later chapters. The theoretically third form of state structure is confederation. This concept is mainly applied to the union of several sovereign states relatively used. This is often in the nature of an international legal relationship to a state's legal relationship. Sometimes confederation as a form used in the transition to a federation possible. The U.S. Confederation, for example, has become a U.S. federation. Today, Switzerland and Canada are confederations, in fact, they are also when all became a federation. The federation used the state structure of the former union. In it the state this form was seen as a way of resolving national issues. The allied republics that were part of the Soviet Union are officially sovereign although a republic, they could not solve anything by themselves independently, internationally could not participate in the relationship. The USSR is an overly centralized union state. Any country, including Uzbekistan, is in a certain

geographical location within defined limits. This is the territory of the country. Having a clearly demarcated territory is an indicator of a state as a state is one of the main conditions. There can be no state without a definite territory. The state is clear operates in one territory and the state activity operates in that territory. Territory is a state-owned area. The territory is beyond the boundaries of earth, water, and sky consists of. Depending on the size of the territory of each country, its population, are subdivided into appropriate sections. These fragments are in several stages. Each of them has its own territory (border). Territory of the country division into subdivisions, with perfect organization of public administration. It is a very important state-legal institution. Strengthened at the constitutional level. A separate fourth chapter of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its two chapters (XVI, XVII - chapters) are administrative-territorial and state structure issues. Administrative-territorial in its separate articles structural issues are regulated by law. In determining the administrative-territorial structure of each country, the whole territory easy to manage, effective central influence on the ground, the people. Proximity to government agencies, efficient organization of production, low cost efficiency, the level of supply of raw materials to industry, the tradition of the population takes into account customs, values, historical experience and establishes administrative-territorial units of its choice. Administrative-territorial structure is a social that is resolved on a constitutional basis relations. Therefore, Article 68 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Regions, districts, towns, villages, auls of the Republic of Uzbekistan,

as well as the Republic of Karakalpakstan. This firstly, what the territory of Uzbekistan consists of, and secondly Indicates the administrative units of the territory of Uzbekistan. These include the legal status of territorial units, territorial status, population, 271 differ in the production of material goods or in the occupation of the population does. To the level of the legal status of administrative-territorial units of Uzbekistan can be divided into three parts. The first is the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the regions and the city of Tashkent. The second is districts and cities. Towns to the third, villages and auls. Although the district and the city are administrative-territorial units of the same status, they are social life, people's main occupations, participation in production depending on the situation. Districts are mainly agricultural, cities are engaged in industrial production. Also to the district There are also subordinate cities and districts of city status, of which the status of the scope of activity is determined. The administrative-territorial structure of Uzbekistan is a three-tier administrative unit consists of: the first regions, the city of Tashkent; the second is districts and cities; the third is towns, villages, and auls. The Republic of Karakalpakstan belongs to the first group in terms of administrative-territorial division. So, the first group is high level, the second group is medium level, the third group is low level consists of administrative units. In addition, districts, which are part of the region, ie subordinate to the region, districts within the city, ie subordinate to the city. It's the same as well as cities to the republic, to the province, to

the district cities of subordination. One city in the republic - Tashkent is the only one subordinate to the republic is a city. That is why its status is equated to the provinces. In the Republic, as well as in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, to the region As a rule, the population of the subordinate cities is at least thirty thousand which has a certain administrative significance, promising economic and cities that are considered cultural centers may be included. That is, the city is known to be a city under the jurisdiction of the province have a large population; it is of great administrative importance need; should be the center of culture, the prospect of economic development. Inclusion of cities in the category of cities of regional subordination, their reorganization at the request of the relevant regional governors By the Oliy Majlis in accordance with the proposal of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic is done. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, cities are subordinated to the republic inclusion in the category of cities, their reorganization The Republic of Karakalpakstan will be carried out by the Jogorku Kenesh at the suggestion of the Government To determine the administrative-territorial structure of the Republic of Uzbekistan name of administrative-territorial units and population points in targeted relations The procedure for issuing and renaming is also regulated by this law. According to the law, provinces, districts, cities are named and named after them renaming at the request of the relevant regional governors. It is done by the Assembly.

References:

1. O .T. Khusanov, "Constitutional law of the Republic of Uzbekistan", textbook, Tashkent-2012.
2. A. Jalilov, U. Muhammadiyev, "Fundamentals of Civil Society", textbook, Tashkent-2015
3. M.Mamasidikov, Z.Esanova, D.Habibullayev, "Civil procedural law" textbook, Tashkent- "ILM ZIYO'- 2012
4. X.T. Odilkariyev, "Theory of State and Law", textbook, Tashkent "Justice" 2018.
5. D.Karkhodjayev, A.Akayeva, Sh.Yuldasheva, Textbook "Civil and family law", TASHKENT - "ILM ZIYO" - 2012.
6. Ziyonet. Uz.